

National Partnership for Ocean Prediction: Workshop on Seasonal to Centennial Marine Prediction, 6-7th June 2022

Report authors: R.J. Perks¹, J. Tinker¹, J. Amies¹, A. Katavouta², S. Wakelin², J. Graham³, Y. Artioli⁴, K. Haines⁵, R. Wood¹

¹Met Office, Exeter, UK

²National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool, UK

³Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK

⁴Plymouth Marine Laboratory, Plymouth, UK

⁵University of Reading, Reading, UK

Executive Summary

The National Partnership for Ocean Prediction (NPOP) organised a workshop on 6-7 June 2022 at Reading University, to bring together UK scientists and stakeholders involved in prediction and projection of the marine environment on seasonal to centennial timescales, including the effects of climate variability and change. Financial contributions to the workshop scoping and organisation were provided by NPOP, the Met Office Hadley Centre Climate Programme (funded by BEIS), and the SPF UK Climate Resilience Programme (funded by UKRI).

The motivation for the workshop was the recognition that the UK has a strong but fragmented scientific community working in this area, and a perception of a need for marine prediction information that could not be met by a single institution. Workshop objectives were:

- Understand the current state of science for marine projections, including key knowledge gaps identified by IPCC AR6 WG1 and II.
- Bring together the relevant strands of marine research in the UK to promote future scientific collaboration, identify research priorities and explore new opportunities.
- Discuss research priorities for any possible future updates to UK Climate Projections, and identify ways in which the wider UK academic community could contribute.
- Explore how we can continue to work productively together going forward to deliver the maximum value to society, and how the NPOP Activity Group can help.

The workshop consisted of a combination of invited speakers/plenary discussions, and topic-specific breakout groups. While the breakout groups were focused on user priorities and scientific opportunities, user perspectives were also addressed in three of the invited speaker sessions.

The body of this report includes detailed notes on the discussions. While much of the discussion focused on projections of the impacts of climate change on the marine environment (i.e. several decades ahead), several interventions emphasised the importance of considering this alongside shorter term (seasonal to decadal) predictions.

Overall there was a high level of enthusiasm from the participants to develop the UK's activity in this area, and a recognition of the value of a more coordinated approach. Two specific actions emerged:

1. Convene a small cross-institutional working group to develop a proposed roadmap for UK marine climate change projections, suitable to inform upcoming rounds of the UK's Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA). *[In progress Spring 2024]*
2. Explore ideas for the ongoing activities of the NPOP Seasonal-to-Centennial Activity Group, to build and maintain an active scientific community in this area.

1. Introduction

All aspects of the marine environment are vulnerable to climate variability and change. Changes to atmospheric conditions drive changes in the physical ocean, changing the interaction between the tides, mean sea-level, storms and waves, which in turn have significant impacts on the coastal environment. The United Kingdom Climate Projections 2018 (hereafter UKCP18) Marine Report (Palmer et al., 2018) found that sea-level rise is the primary mechanism to affect coastal flood risk on multi-decadal timescales. For offshore marine operations such as shipping and renewable energy, the response of the storm track under climate change is an important consideration as this affects the surge and wave characteristics (Figure 1). Whereas changes to sea water temperature and salinity can be considered the most important aspect of climate change when thinking about marine ecosystem services.

Sea-level rise and marine information are important for decision making across sectors. It can inform climate change mitigation policy by helping understand the consequences of different emission pathway choices, and can be used within local adaptation and resilience planning and national scale risk assessments.

The marine research community aims to describe, explain and predict the societally relevant

aspects of climate change impacts on the whole of the marine environment.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of climate change in coastal and shelf seas. Source: Keynote talk, Decadal to Centennial Marine Climate Impacts Projections, J. Holt (NOC)

The National Partnership for Ocean Prediction (NPOP), Marine Predictions of Seasonal to Centennial Timescales working group held a two-day meeting on Monday 6th and Tuesday 7th June 2022. The meeting was hosted at the University of Reading and included 44 registered participants, from the marine science community of the UK and select government departments. The workshop aims were:

- Understand the current state of science for marine projections, including key knowledge gaps identified in IPCC AR6 WGI and II.
- Bring together the relevant strands of marine research in the UK to promote future scientific collaboration, identify research priorities and explore new opportunities.
- Discuss research priorities for any possible future updates to UK Climate Projections, and identify ways in which the wider UK academic community could contribute.
- Explore how we can continue to work productively together going forward to deliver the maximum value to society, and how the NPOP Activity Group can help.

The workshop programme was structured as follows (Appendix 1). Session 1 included a general introduction to the NPOP, followed by the first two keynote talks on the topic of 'Underpinning Science', focusing on the current state of marine science and possible gaps for future research. Session 2 kicked off the second keynote topic of 'User Needs' relevant to seasonal to centennial marine predictions and commenced the first breakout discussion session based on three topics: i) the physical ocean, ii) biogeochemistry and, iii) compound events. On the second day,

Session 3 highlighted the 'UK Climate Projections 2018 (UKCP18) and potential future updates' in the third keynote topic and the 'Policy Requirements' in the fourth and final keynote talk. The final session included more breakout discussion sessions on three more topics: i) coastal impacts, ii) waves and surge and, iii) atmospheric and climatic drivers. At the end of the two days, all of the sessions were summarised by way of a panel discussion with the keynote speakers.

This workshop report is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a summary of the keynote talks, Section 3 provides an overview of the main discussion points during the breakout sessions and Section 4 comments on the next steps for the working group.

2. Presentation summaries

Across the two days there were four keynote topics i) Underpinning science, ii) User needs, iii) UKCP18 and potential future science, and iv) Policy needs. These topics were covered in five presentations, each of which were followed by a Q&A discussion. Highlights from each of the presentations are provided below, along with a short description on the main points from the discussion.

2.1. Decadal to Centennial Marine Climate Impacts Projections, J. Holt (NOC)

Highlights:

- Global climate models (GCMs) are not adequate to describe the majority of regional impacts caused by climate change, as such there is a need for dynamical downscaling.
- In general, GCMs have insufficient resolution and a lack of process representation
 - GCMs also have regional biases due to multi-centennial spin up and observational constraints.
- CMIP5 models generally perform worse in the coastal regions than in the open ocean. Most of the CMIP5 models overestimate the seasonal cycle meaning it is difficult to use them for realistic projections.
- Dynamical downscaling can be described as higher resolution regional model simulations that are forced by atmospheric and ocean boundary conditions from lower resolution global models such as CMIP6.
- The protocols and pitfalls of downscaling have been discussed extensively in a workshop that looked at state of the art analysis of 100+ studies from 1998-2021 (Drenkard et al 2021).

Example or upcoming projects:

- CANARI – Climate Change in the Arctic-North Atlantic Region and Impacts on the UK
- CHAMFER – UK Coastal Hazards: Multi-hazard controls on Flooding and Erosion
- FLAME – Future Coastal Ocean Climates (UN Decade endorsed programme, part of CoastPredict).

Points raised in discussion:

- The talk focused on the need for downscaling global models. However transient simulations with regionally downscaled models are still relatively coarse and they are

computationally expensive. One solution to this is to use a "timeslice" approach, to perform simulations with higher resolution at specific time periods (e.g., 1960-1990 and 2070-2100 rather than a continuous 1960-2010 simulation) and is computationally cheaper. Another solution would be to consider the use of statistical downscaling or machine learning.

- Over the next 10 years, in order to more accurately predict changes in the North Atlantic, there was a consensus that the use of ensembles should be prioritised (over for example going to higher resolution models). Particularly regional ensembles forced with boundary conditions from CMIP6 Earth System Models, as they capture structural uncertainty.
- It is also possible to weight the ensemble of regional model projections based on the accuracy of the Earth system models that are used to drive it, however, this needs to be completed carefully. It should be noted that there may still be tails outside of current ensemble range.
- When considering first order uncertainty, it is usually a result of what model is being used. This is a relatively new area of research that the community has only started to explore.

2.2. Marine predictions: current state, gaps and future challenges, J. Blackford (PML)

Highlights:

- Coupled models enable us to look at a whole list of topics comprehensively, including but not limited to blue carbon, energy security and resource management.
- Multi-model ensembles e.g. Services based on Ecosystem data AssiMiLation: Essential Science and Solutions (SEAMLESS)¹, incorporate a range of different models and can be used to simulate changes across a range of variables.
- Emulators based on machine learning can provide a large ensemble of climate projections but with low computational cost.
- Digital twins of the ocean can be used as a decision support tool to enable stakeholders in ocean protection.
- The main future aim is to prioritise work on setting-up coastal Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPS) that aim to provide useful assessment of climate change on coastal scales.

¹ <https://seamlessproject.org/>

- There are a number of challenges for current and future research around stakeholder engagement, the fragmentation around funding sources and time to act.

Example or upcoming projects:

- eCSE – project to optimise NEMO-FABM

Points raised in discussion:

- Upscaling of climate services such as the Plymouth operational model is not feasible for the entire UK coastline. Future climate services of this nature could focus on key locations that are stakeholder driven.
- The ambition is to have model projections with high resolution covering the whole coast of the UK however, this is not currently feasible in terms of computational time and there may be locations where this is unnecessary.
- The balance of resolution should be considered in light of the problem that is trying to be addressed, e.g. smaller scale processes should not be ignored when thinking about impacts but shortcuts can be considered based on previous model experiments.
- There are opportunities for private sector investment, an example of this is from the carbon capture and storage project. It is important to improve the dialogue and learn their language. In general, the demand for information is increasing.

2.3. User needs, P. Buckley (MCCIP)

Highlights:

- The Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership (MCCIP) brings together scientists, government departments and NGOs to provide impartial advice feeds into the UK's state of the seas reporting and helps researchers demonstrate impact.
- The key challenges and emerging issues are:
 - Building the evidence base
 - Understanding the drivers and associated impact
 - Explaining uncertainty in climate change projections
 - Fulfilling commitment.
- Timescales of interest vary depending on sector (Figure 2). For example, fisheries are interested in future storminess in the short term, whereas insurance companies are showing interest in marine information on the longer time horizons.

- There are different types of Marine Protected Areas, which can create challenges when trying to engage with them.

Figure 2: Timeline of user needs for marine predictions and projections. Source: Keynote talk, User needs, P. Buckley (MCCIP)

Example or upcoming projects include (the current focus of MCCIP):

- Move to 'rolling' updates model of evidence provision
- A new web interface to enhance user experience
- Key challenges and emerging issues outputs
- Build on international work
- Greater focus on adaptation and mitigation work

Points raised in discussion:

- Councils/authorities may be more interested in short-term predictions, but they do understand the need to build robustness to climate change.
- Development of new infrastructure often requires assessment of worst case scenarios. However, commercial contracts may mean such studies (or associated data) are not publicly available.

- Many users are interested in better representation of terrestrial runoff and how this combines with marine aspects to cause impacts.
- If the scientific community needed to pick between attribution studies or prediction, then prediction would be more useful for the majority of users.
- Stakeholder groups such as fisheries and aquaculture are interested in multiple timescales.

2.4. UK Climate Projections 2018 (UKCP18) and potential future updates, J. Lowe and M. Palmer (Met Office)

Highlights:

- UKCP18 summarised the coastal and marine information for mitigation (understand consequences of pathway choices) and adaptation (national risk assessment and local finer scale details). The marine aspects focussed on mean sea level and drivers of extreme coastal water levels.
- Access to UKCP18 data is through a user interface (20% of these users are in flood and coastal management), and CEDA (generally more experienced data users).
- For engaging with policy makers, scientists need to speak their language. The use of storylines (a narrative of possible change) and using warming levels instead of scenarios are more easily understood by policy and decision makers.
- It would be good to have a consistent set of simulations to inform impacts studies
 - Consistent global climate model (e.g. HadGEM3) used to drive other models
 - It is important to integrate the land component in our coastal simulations (e.g., rivers outflow).
- A Sea level workshop was held in Sept 2021 which included government stakeholders (e.g. BEIS, EA) and scientists/users focusing on stakeholder perspectives, scientific gaps and next steps ([Sept 2021 Workshop | Sea Level Workshops \(exeter.ac.uk\)](https://www.exeter.ac.uk/research/centres/sea-level-workshops/)).

Example or upcoming projects include:

- Where next (short term):
 - The main focus for the Met Office is to make what's already there more useful.
- Where next (5+ years):
 - Look for opportunities to bring capability and need together.
 - What can we provide for in situ UK water shelf observations and projections.

- Getting ready for CCRA5 and UNFCC second global stocktake.

Points raised in discussion:

- Co-development of our scientific programmes with the stakeholders is key to working more effectively. Increased interaction with economists and the insurance sector could be beneficial.
- Translating ‘mm of sea level change into associated £s of impacts’, can only be achieved with close interactions with economists. The Met Office is currently talking to government stakeholders in this space. There is value in engaging early with the economists and stakeholders, so we can co-design our programmes and know the required outputs for their needs.
- Translate science into additional useful metrics (cannot solely rely on mm of sea level change or £s of damage). For example, a useful metric for sea level rise would be the number of people’s health affected or total property damages due to flooding.
- If we are thinking in terms of storylines rather than scenarios, we must link warming with a narrative for likelihood of possible effects and changes. Helpful to communicate as “what if” questions.
- The type of early warning depends on decision, what run up times are useful, etc. Co-development again becomes important to identify this. In the short term it is useful to monitor changes in the marine environment in line with projections. It will also be useful to link early warnings to storyline approaches to support communication of risk.

2.5. Policy Requirements, L. Harland (Defra)

Highlights:

- Defra is “responsible for improving and protecting the environment. [They] aim to grow a green economy and sustain thriving rural communities. [They] also support our world-leading food, farming and fishing industries.”
- Defra has a 25 Years Environment Plan that ensures all policies, programmes and decisions consider the possible extent of climate change this century. There is an increased focus on adaptation action.
- The UK marine strategy and marine climate characteristics focus on:
 - Spatio-temporal variation of sea surface temperature
 - Salinity

- Wave height
- Turbidity
- pH.
- The Climate Change Risk Assessments (CCRA) have evolved since their conception. CCRA1 (2012) was a systematic review of over 100 different risks, CCRA2 (2017) shifted the approach to place a greater emphasis on urgency and priorities for the National Adaptation Plan and CCRA3 (2022) had greater accessibility of outputs for the primary audience of government and devolved administrations.
- With respect to adaptation it is useful to provide marine information in the context of climate change at 2C and 4C. This can then be interpreted with regards to what this means for how we develop solutions.
- New areas of interest for resilience and adaptation include acidification and climate shocks and extreme events (e.g., heatwaves and storm surges).
- Most policy is interested in wider impacts to habitats, species, people and infrastructure; it is important to translate science and indicators of physical and biogeochemical changes towards policy interests.

Example or upcoming projects include (Defra engagement):

- MarLIN – Marine Life Information Network – Habitat (biotope) sensitivity assessments for climate change pressures
- SMMR project
- MSPACE - Marine Spatial Planning Addressing Climate Effects

Points raised in discussion:

- There is a clear commitment to focusing on adaptation planning for a 2C and 4C world following advice from the Committee on Climate Change, which can happen on longer timescales. However there is also a need to consider shorter timescales, especially when local thresholds are breached.
- There may be gaps in awareness for policy makers, as such there is a tendency to interact with more comfortable metrics; a lot of Defra's communication with science is through arms length bodies.
- Policy makers often cannot directly interact with scientific data. There is a need for an intermediate step to translate marine datasets to information that is useful for the specific groups.

- Defra is engaged directly with international negotiations and global stocktakes.
- Defra is also interested in 'shock events', but feels there is a bit of a gap within the UK context. For example, heatwaves are not mentioned in MCCIP, but habitats in the UK may be vulnerable to this. Furthermore, there is an interest in the maintenance of natural systems in future. For example, how will sea level change prevent natural systems from sequestering carbon.

3. Discussion sessions

3.1. Biogeochemistry

Key knowledge gaps

- There is a lack of observational data to validate models, particularly those that are at higher resolution.
- A gap exists between the resolution of climate models and stakeholder impact models, such as impact on biological processes. This is evident on temporal and spatial scales.
- Uncertainty needs to be assessed along the entire model chain, from physics to biogeochemistry to impact models.
- It would be useful for there to be a better dialogue between researchers and user groups

Future research priorities

- Many of the gaps are linked with the spatial and temporal resolution of models; this has been identified as a key research priority for biogeochemistry group going forwards.
- It would be beneficial to improve data sharing and data storage options across organisations, by for example light weight tools that address computational cost.
- Uncertainty is a key theme when discussing climate change projections, it is also essential to improve the representation of uncertainty with stakeholder groups.
- Another research priority could be to identify a natural state that the ecosystem can recover to after an impactful event.

Promoting collaboration

- More stakeholder engagement programs like in Environmental risks to infrastructure (ERIIP²).
- Sharing training resources across departments as well as offering information and guidance on useful indicators. This should be across research groups and in collaboration with stakeholder groups.
- Push for the wider marine aspects to be at the front and centre of any future UKCP updates.
- More funding for underpinning science research.

² <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/environmental-risks-to-infrastructure/>

3.2. Physical ocean

Key knowledge gaps

- As with the biogeochemistry breakout group, the physical ocean group also identified a lack of observational data as an important knowledge gap. For example,
 - Shelf circulation is poorly observed.
 - Temperature and salinity are the most observed variables and still the network is sparse, especially as there are no ARGO floats on the North West European Shelf Sea.
 - Stratification (derived from the temperature and salinity observations) is a key parameter, and yet is even more limited.
- The available stratification observations are not detailed enough to be used to initialise model runs or monitor changes, but allows some model evaluation.
 - Currently the model representation of the Shelf stratification processes is imperfect.

Future research priorities

- The Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA) 2 had a summary report on knowledge gaps; it is expected the same or similar will also be completed for CCRA3, which will be useful to identify other research priorities.
- Sometimes it is useful to work backwards to determine research priorities. For example, if a user was interested in the impact of change to offshore winds on wind farms on the NW European shelf, then it would be useful to consider dynamical downscaling of the NW European shelf seas.

Promoting collaboration

- The Met Office, wider research community and funding agencies need to do more user engagement to focus research.
- The Hadley Center Climate Programme (HCCP) has an element of user engagement - this is for both the marine and the land strand.
- A lot of data already exists, it may be useful to consider if there are any 'quick wins' that can be gained from using these data collaboratively.

- If we can demonstrate that decisions are more likely to be made successfully with updated science we are more likely to get research projects funded.

3.3. Compound hazards

Before discussing the key knowledge gaps and future research priorities the compound hazards group thought it important to define what a compound event was. In respect to the following discussions, a compound event could be considered multiple hazardous conditions all occurring at the same time, for example extreme rainfall and a large surge resulting in compound coastal flood inundation. Alternatively, a compound event could be considered as a succession of hazards that accumulate in an impact, for example, poor water quality resulting in an algal bloom and eventually having a negative impact on marine life and human health.

Key knowledge gaps

- There is currently a lack of understanding with respect to the historical extreme events, this is in reference to the drivers of events and of the thresholds of interest when considering impacts.
- Again, there is an issue in validating impact models for extreme events as there are not sufficient bathymetry datasets, or sea level observations to validate the models against.
- In most cases, hourly data is important when looking at compound events and currently these datasets are sparse.

Future research priorities

- There is currently no marine version of the CORDEX project. It would be useful when considering impacts to have a coupled wave-tide-surge modelling suite using the same atmospheric drivers as boundary conditions.
- More research is needed to determine how best we can model coastline change - a number of questions are important to consider here i) should we include wetting and drying, ii) how will bathymetry change as a result of rising sea levels.
- It would be useful to prioritise work looking at how storm tracks will be affected e.g. intensity, duration, trajectory, over the UK as a direct consequence of change to the AMOC.

Promoting collaboration

- There is scope to build upon the National capability project (eg. [UKNCSP](#)).
- Datasets could be more joined up in JASMIN.
- Stakeholder-led research focus, many users of climate information are interested in the local scale, it would be useful to start here and work backwards to climate models to determine what is required.

3.4. Coastal environments

Key knowledge gaps

- The coast is a major environmental interface between land, oceans, seabed, rivers, atmosphere, and humans. Current modelling infrastructure is not able to fully resolve this complexity, through either model coupling or parameterisations.
- Coastal environments fundamentally involve nonlinear processes that span across different environmental domains. Bridging across environmental domains (e.g. land-ocean; river-ocean; ocean-seabed; etc) can be difficult.
- Significant efforts are devoted to capturing shorter time scales e.g. responses to synoptic events. Current modelling approaches and tools of impacts in coastal environments across seasonal to centennial spatial and temporal scales are limited. For example, the impact of coupling across the Shelf has been demonstrated through UKEP, but this is not feasible to run for longer timescales.
- A variety of different user groups are interested in the coast, many of which will be interested in the same climatic driver but a different impact and modelling all of these aspects is difficult. For example, if precipitation amounts are to change in the future, this may affect river flow and in turn nutrient fluxes and storm water flow.

Future research priorities

- It would be useful to have a more consistent set of projections across the marine-land interface. Furthermore, it should be recognised that the marine environment is “downstream” of the land and ideally modelled land outputs should be used as inputs to marine models. It was suggested that the release of climate projection data from land should be staggered to enable more effective use of the datasets in marine modelling.

- It could be more beneficial to focus on high resolution coastal examples, rather than using the computational time to model the entire UK coastline at high resolution.
- Sediments, turbidity and geomorphology are entirely absent from climate projections and the modelling systems underpinning the climate projections. If noted as a priority, it would be worth revisiting the rationale for not including them.
- Exploring the feasibility of a Coastal Model Inter-comparison Project, “Coastal MIP”. This could involve determining best-practice for methodologies going forward (e.g., choice of parameterisations, boundary conditions or surface forcing), and/or comparing high resolution coastal models with lower resolution self-wide configurations.

Promoting collaboration

- More open data sharing would be useful to ensure that all existing data (observations as well as models and reanalysis) can be used effectively to develop coastal models.
- Further collaboration with other disciplines or institutions may help to bridge some of the gaps listed above. Collaborations with:
 - Centre for Ecology and Hydrology,
 - British Geological Survey,
 - DEFRA,
 - Environment Agency,
 - Scottish Environmental Protection Agency,
 - National Resources Wales,
 - NatureScot.

3.5. Atmospheric drivers

Key knowledge gaps

- Persistence is a good predictor of atmospheric conditions in winter, however a knowledge gap here is how it works in summer.
- Marine heatwaves occur as a direct result of air-sea interactions, it would be useful to understand more fully the atmospheric patterns that result in marine heatwaves.
- There was a detailed discussion about where uncertainty in predictions and projections come from on the Shelf.

- Another knowledge gap that was considered was the possible range of conditions that could plausibly occur from a full range of atmospheric drivers.

Future research priorities

- To fill the gap on persistence, it would be possible to complete some seasonal predictions using initial conditions in winter from GloSea.
- It could be useful to make more use of ensembles, particularly to better understand high impact storm events and marine heatwaves.
- Another aspect of future research could consider targeted downscaling of GCMs, but it is important to ensure the right metric is being assessed. For example, it might be most beneficial to downscale metrics that are most appropriate for storylines.
- It would be beneficial to create a flow chart of the key knowledge gaps, the user requirements and link these with the future research priorities, to create a 'roadmap'.

Promoting collaboration

- Throughout all stages of project design the user conversation is important.
- International coordination for marine downscaling within FLAME (should learn from CORDEX), WCRP and Lighthouse.

3.6. Waves and surge

Key knowledge gaps

- There is some knowledge of user groups from across members of NPOP, but it was felt that this was an area that could be improved upon. However, it was noted that some barriers exist when trying to identify users such as anonymity, data protection, google analytics, grey literature.
- There may be gaps in the observational datasets, more importantly the fact that there are multiple data centers (BODC, EmodNet, CCO,) makes it difficult to see the joined-up picture.
 - Buoys and tide gauges are often used but offshore altimeter data and bottom ADCP may be better as these avoid harbour effects.
 - Remote sensing from shore-based radar e.g. X-Band or WireWall.

- There is more to explore in nature-based solutions to coastal defences e.g. seagrass as coastal protections (additional links to blue carbon), natural adaptive methods can also have strong links to policy (potential issues around public perception).
- How renewable energy interacts with the coast, both the influence of climate change on offshore energy and how offshore structures affect coastal dynamics.

Future research priorities

It is important for the waves and surge breakout group that the following research priorities are discussed with users to make sure they are as useful as possible for these groups.

- It may be beneficial to upscale small-scale projects (usually consultancy type projects) to a much wider area.
- Currently, different models are used for marine applications wave/surge and land projections. Would be good to have a consistent set of models, more joined up configurations and more coordination between runs.
- Multi-model ensembles will be useful to address uncertainty in model projections.
- Use of machine learning and emulators as cheaper or more lightweight solutions to do first pass/exploratory work – can then use these to inform model and ensemble selection and guide what modelling should focus on.

Promoting collaboration

- New research projects should aim to involve people who generated input datasets as these people are the experts in this particular area.
- We could learn from previous events or groups that have successfully linked users and scientists e.g., NERC-ERIIP, Oceans of Knowledge (Institute of Marine engineering Science and Technology group).
- Co-ordinate who does what in the UK potentially via the National Climate Science Partnership (NCSP), to try and facilitate collaboration rather than competition for the same funds and same research purposes.

4. Next steps

The workshop brought together a strong but widely dispersed UK science community working in this area, with representatives of the UK marine policy community, and enabled a discussion of how the science community might work together to develop marine predictions and projections that will be useful for policy and decision making. Many participants commented on how refreshing it was to be able to discuss together in person again. Two specific post-actions will be followed up:

1. A small cross-institutional working group will be formed to develop a roadmap for UK marine climate change projections, to provide evidence to inform rounds 4 and 5 of the UK Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA). The wider community will be consulted in this development.
2. Ideas will be explored for ongoing activities of the group to build and maintain an active scientific community in this area. Initial discussion at the Workshop suggested interest in approximately 6-monthly discussion meetings focusing on specific topics.

Acknowledgments

This perspective document arose from discussions during the “National Partnership for Ocean Prediction - Workshop on Seasonal to Centennial Marine Prediction”, held on 6th and 7th June 2022. NPOP, HCCP and SPF funding has contributed to the scoping and organization of the meeting with the event funded through NPOP and HCCP.

References

Drenkard et al 2021 Next-generation regional ocean projections for living marine resource management in a changing climate ICES J. Mar. Sci. doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab100

Palmer, M. D., Howard, T., Tinker, J., Lowe, J., Bricheno, L., Calvert, D., et al. (2018). UKCP18 marine report, 133 pp. Available from:

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/pub/data/weather/uk/ukcp18/science-reports/UKCP18-Marine-report.pdf>

Appendix 1 - Workshop Programme

Day 1: Monday 6th June		
	Session 1	Chair: Keith Haines
10:30-11:20	Registration / Informal coffee, cakes and networking / time to set up posters	
11:20-11:25	Welcome, H&S, housekeeping and agenda - Chair	
11:25-12:00	Introduction to workshop, and goals - Richard Wood	
12:00-12:40	Keynote #1: Underpinning science and marine services - Jason Holt and Jerry Blackford	
12:40-13:00	Q&A #1: Underpinning science and marine services	
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
	Session 2	Chair: Jon Tinker
14:00-14:35	Keynote #2: User requirements - Paul Buckley	
14:35-14:50	Q&A #2: User requirements	
14:50-15:00	Introduction to the afternoon - Chair	

15:00-15:30	Coffee break [additional time to set up posters]
15:30-17:00	Break out discussions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Break out group A: The physical ocean - Jason Holt • Break out group B: Biogeochemistry - James Clark • Break out group C: Compound events - Pete Robbins
17:00-17:25	Break out discussion feedback - volunteer from each group
17:25-17:30	Closing remarks - Chair
17:30-	Posters with drinks available from Park House Bar
19:30-	Conference Dinner

Day 2: Tuesday 7th June	
	Session 3 Chair: Jenny Graham
9:30-9:45	Welcome, re-cap on day 1 and intro to day 2 - Chair
9:45-10:30	Keynote #3: UKCP18 and potential future updates - Jason Lowe and Matt Palmer
10:30-10:45	Q&A #3: UKCP18 and potential future updates
10:45-11:15	Coffee Break [time to take down posters]

11:15-11:45	Keynote #4: Policy requirements - Laura Harland	
11:45-12:00	Q&S #4: Policy requirements	
12:00-12:05	Introduction to the afternoon - Chair	
12:05-12:10	Workshop photo	
12:10-13:10	Lunch	
	Session 4	Chair: Yuri Artioli
13:10-14:40	Break out discussions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Break out group D: Coastal environments - Laurent Amoudry • Break out group E: Waves and surges - Lucy Bricheno • Break out group F: Atmospheric and climatic drivers - Segolene Berthou 	
14:40 -15:10	Break out discussion feedback - volunteer from each group	
15:10-16:00	Workshop closing remarks - Panel Discussion with keynotes - Chair, Richard Wood [coffee at the back]	
16:00	Close of workshop	

Appendix 2 - Participants

Organising Committee:

- Richard Wood Met Office: Chair of NPOP Activity Group on Seasonal to Centennial Predictions
- Rachel Perks Met Office: Co-chair
- Jonathan Tinker Met Office: Co-chair
- Keith Haines University of Reading: Local organisation lead
- Yuri Artioli Plymouth Marine Laboratory
- Jennifer Graham Cefas
- Sarah Wakelin National Oceanography Centre

Keynote Speakers:

- Jason Holt National Oceanography Centre
- Jerry Blackford Plymouth Marine Laboratory
- Paul Buckley Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership and Cefas
- Jason Lowe Met Office and University of Leeds
- Matt Palmer Met Office and University of Bristol
- Laura Harland Defra

The workshop involved 44 registered participants from the following organisations:

- Bangor University
- Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (Cefas)
- Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra)
- Marine Scotland
- Met Office
- Marine Climate Change Impacts Partnership (MCCIP)
- National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
- National Oceanography Centre (NOC)
- Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML)
- Scottish Environment Protection Agency
- University of Reading